

Blockchain-based Traceability for Food Supply Chains:

The ALLIANCE approach

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7 Food Supply Chains in different countries

Pilots

PDO/PGI Extra Virgin Olive Oil @ Biocos, Italy

PDO Feta Cheese @ Olympos, Greece

Organic Honey @ WBP, France

PGI Faba Beans @ ASINCAR, Spain

PGI Lika Potatoes @ UPLK, Croatia

Organic Pasta @ Alce Nero, Italy

PDO Arilje Raspberry @ Original, Serbia

ALLIANCE Architecture

Key Technologies

Blockchain Technology

Enhancing traceability with **tamper-proof records**, enabling transparency and verifying authentication of claims

AI Early Warning System:

Analyzing data performance metrics from various steps in the food value chain and **detecting patterns and anomalies** indicative of food fraud in real-time, offering timely decision making to food actors

Next-Gen Portable DNA Sequencing

For verification of the geographic origin of EVOO and honey correlating specific genetic markers **confirming the authenticity of the product**

Predictive Analytics

Forecasting future risks with **historical and real-time data analysis** and identifying high-risk areas to proactively countermeasure vulnerabilities in the supply chain

Digital Knowledge Base

Providing and sharing **comprehensive information on food products**, supply chain practices, and known fraud incidences, informing involved stakeholders and actors

ALLIANCE Architecture focused on Blockchain

Blockchain

Blockchain Technology

Enhancing traceability with **tamper-proof records**, enabling transparency and verifying authentication of claims

On-chain Blockchain

- Immutable record keeping
- Distributed replicas of the same data

Off-chain Database

- Time-responsive data storage
- Single point of failure

Blockchain dual data storage

On-chain & Off-chain

- Firstly, data are stored to **off-chain**.
- Then, if they are critical, they are **queued** to be stored to on-chain, under the form of **transactions**.
- One of the peers, submits the transactions to the **ordering service**.
- The ordering service creates the **new block** which is linked to the other blocks.
 - Creating a **chain of blocks**, a.k.a. blockchain.
- The block is **propagated to all peers** with strong consistency (Raft consensus).

Blockchain dual data storage

On-chain offloading

- Files with large size are stored **only to off-chain**.
- On-chain stores their **hash values**, and **links** to their buffers in off-chain.
- Hash value is significantly smaller than the actual file.
- If somebody changes the file in off-chain, the modification can be detected by the change of the hash value.

Blockchain dual data storage

MQTT Broker

Traceability support

Olive oil chain

- Ingredients or intermediate sub-products involved in olive oil chain are **uniquely identified**.
- At each stage of the chain, the resulting data of this stage includes the **identifiers of the output of the previous stage**.
- Olive oil products are categorized into **batches**.
- Each batch is the result of a **unique milling process** that took place at a particular milling facility.
- This milling operation had crushed the entire quantity or a portion of the olives that were received at a **specific date-time**.

Traceability support

Information at Olive oil chain

- System provides for each bottle of olive oil (specified by LOT):
 - the **time** that this oil was **produced**,
 - the **milling facility** used for its production,
 - the **times** that olives have been **received**,
 - the **fields** that generated these olives,
 - the olive fruit **characteristics**,
 - the **DNA-based IoT** measurements,
 - the **quality control** outcomes.

Lot

Lot Name: **LOT-OVTOEU**
DNA Test Conducted: **Yes**
DNA Result: **Positive**

Milling

Milling Datetime: **25/02/2025**
Visual Description: **Passed Visual Inspection**
DNA Test Conducted: **Yes**
DNA Result: **Positive**
Chemical Analysis Conducted: **Yes**

Olive

Field Code: **ROSSI-10**
Harvesting Datetime: **24/02/2025**
Harvested Variety: **Moraiolo**
Pigment: **Brown/Black**
DNA Test Conducted: **Yes**
DNA Result: **Positive**

Storage

Storage Datetime: **26/02/2025**
DNA Test Conducted: **Yes**
DNA Result: **Positive**

Reception

Reception Datetime: **25/02/2025**
Facility Code: **FRANTOIO-03**

Blockchain web-app

Feta cheese chain – Milk collection

ALLIANCE

Supply Chains

Milk Collection

Milk Transportation

Milk Reception

Milk Pasteurization

Cheese Production

Cheese Storage

Cheese Distribution

Quality Control

PDO Feta Cheese Supply Chain

Add new milk collection Add new milk transportation

Producer	Type of Milk	Temperature (C)	pH	Quantity (L)	Visual Inspection	Ice Bowl Code	Sample Bottle Code	Transported	Date
No data available									

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- Screenshot depicting the **web-app** for **feta cheese chain**.
- The **administrator** has **access to all**, whilst **other roles** have **restricted authority** and access to the data of specific stages.
 - The farmers can view the tabs ‘Milk Collection’.
 - The same tab is inaccessible to the staff who oversee feta cheese storage.

Blockchain web-app

Feta cheese chain – Milk transportation

ALLIANCE

- Supply Chains
- Milk Collection
- Milk Transportation**
- Milk Reception
- Milk Pasteurization
- Cheese Production
- Cheese Storage
- Cheese Distribution
- Quality Control

PDO Feta Cheese Supply Chain

Milk Transportations

Numberplate	Quantity (L)	Received
new feta truck	1000	No

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- The **truck drivers**, who transport milk from fields to silos, can see the active transportations and the contents of each transportation by clicking on the desired record.

Blockchain web-app

Feta cheese chain – Milk reception

ALLIANCE

- Supply Chains
- Milk Collection
- Milk Transportation
- Milk Reception**
- Milk Pasteurization
- Cheese Production
- Cheese Storage
- Cheese Distribution
- Quality Control

PDO Feta Cheese Supply Chain

Add Milk Reception Log Milk Sample

Milk Receptions

Numberplate	Quantity (L)	Stored Quantity (L)
No data available		
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- The **reception manager** declares a new reception at the facility, through clicking on the ‘Add Milk Reception’ button.
- Once the user selects a truck, (s)he also provides the required information and the contents are uploaded and displayed on the web-app.

Blockchain web-app

Retailer chain

ALLIANCE

- Supply Chains
- Warehouse Mana...
- Storage
- Distribution
- Market

Masoutis

Add new Reception

Awaiting Acceptance

Supply Chain	Temperature	Hygenic Condition	Labelling	Quantity	Registration	Accepted	Accept	Details
Olive Oil			26/02/2025	14	LOT-AXFDJZ	No	<button>Accept</button>	<button>View Details</button>
Olive Oil			26/02/2025	19	LOT-UNFUGS	No	<button>Accept</button>	<button>View Details</button>
Olive Oil			26/02/2025	35	LOT-TALDNI	No	<button>Accept</button>	<button>View Details</button>
Olive Oil			26/02/2025	65	LOT-WBUXVP	No	<button>Accept</button>	<button>View Details</button>

- Screenshot depicting the **web-app** for **retailer distribution chain**.
- The ‘Distribution Manager’ of olive oil chain has updated the system that the olive oil products have been prepared and are in the process of being distributed to the retailing points of Masoutis.
- The ‘Warehouse Manager’ of Masoutis receives the product descriptions according to the **GS1 EPCIS standard**.
- As soon as the trucks transporting olive oil bottles arrive at Masoutis warehouse, the manager checks if the received products correspond to their EPCIS description and either approves or changes the relevant data.

Interoperability

GS1 EPCIS

- **GS1 EPCIS** standard provides a description of **business steps** in a supply chain, called **EPCIS events**.
- The description of an EPCIS event answers:
 - **What** (is this event)?
 - **When** (is it happened)?
 - **Where** (is it took place)?
 - **Why** (is this happened)?
- In our solution, we used EPCIS for visualizing the data at point **V3** of the supply chain
- The retailer receives food products of all 7 supply chains, but their description is **unified** under the EPCIS standard.

Events Info		
Event Type	ObjectEvent	ADD
Event ID		
WHAT	EPCs	EPCs (Count: 1) https://id.gs1.org/01/09521568336451/21/0
	Quantities	
WHEN	Event Time	2025-05-09T11:45:27+03:00
	Record Time	2025-05-09T12:12:58+03:00
WHERE	Read Point	https://id.gs1.org/414/1234567891231/254
	Business Location	
WHY	Business Step	commissioning
	Disposition	active
	Persistent Disposition	
	Business Transactions	
	Source	
HOW		
OTHER		

ALLIANCE

Thank you

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